

Popular Article

Summer Anestrus: How to Get Rid of it in Buffaloes

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Abstract

Summer anestrus is a common reproductive problem commonly reported in buffaloes. It is mainly due to endocrinological disturbances in the buffaloes ultimately causing huge losses to the farmers in terms of the economy. Heat stress produced during summer also affects folliculo-genesis, follicular fluid microenvironment and oocyte quality. A large number of hormonal regimens have been used with varying degrees of efficacy in terms of estrus induction and conception rate. A combined strategy of improvement in environment, nutrition and management is a pre-requisite for hormonal manipulation to improve productivity in summer anestrus buffaloes. A brief description of summer anestrus with special reference to factors responsible, endocrinology, deleterious effects on reproductive system and possible remedial measures are presented in this article.

Introduction

Due to their enormous productivity potential, buffaloes are referred to as "Black Gold" in the Indian subcontinent. The buffaloes are reared extensively in the Asian subcontinent due to their better milk fat yielding characteristic. The species has a reputation for being a poor breeder, with low fertility in the majority of environments where it is raised (Barile, 2005). They are several innate reproductive issues associated with the buffaloes among which summer anestrus is also a major one. Practically, in all the sections of the country, domestic buffaloes cease to reproduce during the summer. Summer anestrus is the common name for this illness, which affects 36.6 to 59.5% of buffaloes. Because of an abnormal endocrine profile that causes ovarian inactivity, buffaloes with summer anestrus do not show estrus. Increased day length combined with high ambient temperature produces hyperprolactinemia, which suppresses gonadotropin release and alters ovarian steroidogenesis. Folliculo-genesis, the follicular fluid micro-environment, and oocyte quality are all affected by heat stress. Environmental, dietary, hormonal, and managemental factors all play a role in summer anestrus.

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Factors affecting buffaloes during summer

A) Environmental Factors

During the summer, due to high ambient temperature and relative humidity, the breeding efficiency of the buffaloes get affected along with the aberration in the duration of the estrus cycle (Pandey and Roy, 1966, Roy *et al.*, 1968). Prolonged exposure to direct sun rays is supposed to have a direct effect on the neuro-endocrine setup which ultimately lead to the aberration in the estrus cycle (Razdan, 1988).

Fig.1: Influence of Heat Stress on fertility (Pratap P. *et al.*, 2017)

B) Nutritional Factors

In general, dietary factors in bovines are blamed for anestrus. However, diet is only one of the factors that contribute to seasonality in buffalo reproduction (Zicarelli, 1997). During the summer season, the forages particularly in the tropical region undergo lignification process and become a deficit in the minerals ultimately causing ovarian inactivity in the forage-dependent animal(s). The serum levels of Zn, Cu, and Co in anestrus buffaloes have also been found to be lower than usual (Singh *et al.*, 2006). Iron and copper are commonly utilized as indicators for FSH, LH, and estrogen activity, and are detected in lower concentrations in anestrus buffaloes as compared to cyclic animals. Anestrus was reported to be caused by phosphorus shortage and hypocuprosis due to a low copper–molybdenum ratio during the summer (Randhawa *et al.*, 2004).

C) Endocrine Factors

Heat stress is a crucial factor in buffalo's reduced fertility during the late summer months. Heat stress has a direct impact on reproductive hormones and other physiological systems as a result of an increase in body temperature (De Rensis and Scaramuzzi, 2003; Khodaei Motlagh, 2003). The prolactin is directly related to ambient temperature and mediates the seasonal effects on buffalo reproduction (Singh and Chaudhry, 1992). During the summer season, the buffaloes exhibit the alterations in the pineal metabolism which is responsible for hyperprolactinaemia and ultimately a probable cause of summer anestrus in the species.

C) Managemental Factors

During the summer, management plays a vital part in buffalo rearing. During the summer, the majority of buffalo exhibit silent estrus, which is characterized by less strong indications of estrus and shorter duration (Jainudeen and Hafez, 2000). It was discovered that buffaloes tend to show estrus predominantly at night or early in the morning, which goes unreported by most farmers. As a result, routine surveillance is ineffective in detecting estrus in buffaloes resulting in a longer service time during the warmer months (Buglio *et al.*, 2000).

Strategies for Overcoming Summer Anestrus

A) Managemental Practices

Summer buffalo breeding can be successfully carried out by modifying farm management procedures. In order to increase the efficiency of rural buffaloes breeding reared in the field during the hot summer months, the basis of real management is to protect the species from direct sun radiation, which includes providing shade, a loose housing structure, and applying water to the body surface by sprinkling, washing, or offering to wallow. Showers, in addition to wallowing facilities, have been demonstrated to increase the calving rate. A well-designed and comprehensive housing system, as well as a transition from day to night grazing, aid in mitigating the negative impacts on buffalo fertility and productivity during the breeding season.

B) Improving estrus detection methods

One of the variables that increase the calving conception interval in buffalo is poor estrus detection. The typical heat detection procedures employed in buffalo are ineffective in detecting estrus during the summer season (Jainudeen and Hafez, 2000), hence using an entire male during the cooler hours of the day such as early morning or night may increase estrus detection efficacy. To discover buffaloes in estrus in the field, it would be useful to observe the animal at night and early in the morning for symptoms of estrus.

C) Hormonal treatments

To relieve anestrus and increase ovarian activity, and initiate or synchronize behavioral estrus, a variety of hormone therapy regimens are used (Barile, 2005). Various hormones, either alone or in combination, were administered with varying degrees of success. Progesterone-based treatment regimens (PRID, CIDR, CRESTAR, Progesterone injections) are very effective in inducing ovarian activity in summer anestrus buffaloes, either alone or in combination with gonadotropins and PGF2.

Fig.2: Controlled Internal Drug Release (CIDR) with CIDR Applicator

D) Nutritional management

Heat stress in buffaloes can be reduced by providing a roughage diet during night hours and grazing in the morning and late afternoon hours only. Furthermore, summer reproduction efficiency is improved by feeding green fodder, silage, or hay, as well as ad-libitum water and mineral mixture supplementation (Harjit and Arora, 1982). Minerals must be supplemented in grazing animals, especially those that are poor in forages or fodders, and the energy balance in the ration must be maintained.

E) Herbal treatment

In practice; 45.00 percent by feeding boiled methi with wheat bran for three days; 38.84 percent by feeding 0.5–1 kg boiled bajra mixed with jaggery is used to reduce the effect of summer.

Conclusion

Buffaloes with summer anestrus fail to exhibit estrus as a result of aberration in the endocrine profile leading to ovarian inactivity. Increased day length with high environmental temperature causes hyperprolactinemia, suppressing the secretion of gonadotrophins, which leads to an alteration in ovarian steroidogenesis. Heat stress produced during summer also affects folliculogenesis, follicular fluid microenvironment, and oocyte quality. A large number of hormonal regimens have been used with varying degrees of efficacy in terms of estrus induction and

conception rate. A combined strategy of improvement in environment, nutrition, and management is a prerequisite for hormonal manipulation to improve productivity in summer anestrus buffaloes.

References

- Barile VL. 2005. Improving reproductive efficiency in female buffaloes. *Livestk Prod Sci.* 92:83–194.
- Bughio S, Shahani AK, Mirani AH, Moriani AA, Oad FC, Bughio BA. 2000. Seasonal trend of calving and subsequent service period in buffaloes. *Pak J Biol Sci.* 3:2169–2170.
- De Rensis F, Scaramuzzi RJ. 2003. Heat stress and seasonal effects on reproduction in the dairy cow: a review. *Theriogenology.* 60:1139–1151.
- Harjit K, Arora SP. 1982. Influence of level of nutrition and season on estrous cycle and fertility in buffaloes. *Buffalo Bull.* 1:15.
- Jainudeen MR, Hafez ESE. 2000. Reproductive cycles in cattle and buffaloes. In: Hafez ESE, Hafez B, editors. *Reproduction in farm animals.* 7th ed. Baltimore (Maryland): Lea and Febiger; p. 297–314.
- Khodaei Motlagh M. 2003. Study of some effective factors in reproductive performance of Iranian Holstien cows thesis animal physiology. Iran: Tehran University.
- Pandey MD, Roy A. 1966. Vitamin A and carotene status of domestic ruminants and the effects of seasons on vitamin A storage in buffaloes. *Indian Vet J.* 43:613–621.
- Pragna, P., Archana, P. R., Aleena, J., Sejian, V., Krishnan, G., Bagath, M., ... & Bhatta, R. (2017). Heat stress and dairy cow: Impact on both milk yield and composition.
- Randhawa CS, Randhawa SS, Singh N, Sidhu SS. 2004. Copper supplementation and fertility response in anestrus buffaloes – a clinical trial. *Indian J AnimReprod.* 25:41–42.
- Razdan MN. 1988. Buffalo performance in relation to climatic environment. *Proceedings of Second World Buffalo Congress, Vol 2, Part 1; Dec 12–16; New Delhi, India.* p. 173–186.
- Roy A, Raizada BC, Tiwari RBL, Pandey MD, Yadav PC, Sengupta BP. 1968. Effect of management on fertility of buffalo cows bred during summer. *Indian J Vet Sci.* 38:554–560.
- Singh AP, Sah RS, Singh RB, Akhtar MH, Roy GP, Singh C, Kunj V. 2006. Response of mineral mixture, prajana and gn rhon serum biochemical constituents and conception rate in anestrus buffalo. *Indian J AnimReprod.* 27:51–54.
- Singh B, Chaudhry KC. 1992. Plasma hormonal and electrolyte alterations in cycling buffaloes (*Bubalus bubalis*) during hot summer months. *Int J Biometereol.* 36:151–154.
- Zicarelli L 1997. Reproductive seasonality in buffalo. *Proceedings of Third International Course of Biotechnology in Buffalo Reproduction; Oct 6–10; Napoli: Suppl. BubalusBubalis.* Vol. 4. p. 29–52.